

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF OVARIAN CYST – A CASE REPORT**Dr. Sayali Vengurlekar***

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Ovarian cysts are a frequent gynecological condition, often managed with hormonal therapy or surgery in modern medicine. Ayurveda interprets such conditions in relation to Yonivyapad or Granthi, attributing their origin to Kapha-Vata imbalance and derangement of Artavavaha srotas. This report explores an Ayurvedic approach in the management of an ovarian cyst. **Methods:** A 24 years female patient diagnosed with an ovarian cyst was treated with a combination of Shodhana (purificatory measures) and Shamana (pacifying therapy). The protocol included herbal formulations with Kapha-Vata pacifying, Agnivardhana and Srotoshodhaka (channel-cleansing) properties. Dietary regulations and lifestyle modifications were also advised. **Results:** The patient reported relief in symptoms such as pelvic pain, abdominal heaviness,

and menstrual irregularities. Follow-up ultrasonography demonstrated regression of the ovarian cyst, with no adverse effects observed during the treatment. **Discussion:** It suggests that Ayurvedic interventions may effectively address ovarian cysts by correcting dosha imbalance, improving Agni, and restoring normal reproductive physiology. This case emphasizes the potential of Ayurveda as a safe, non-invasive alternative in managing ovarian cysts, meriting further clinical research for wider validation.

KEYWORDS: Ovarian cyst, Ayurveda, Yonivyapad, Shodhana, Shamana, Case report.

INTRODUCTION

Ovarian cysts are fluid-filled sacs that develop within or on the ovary, frequently encountered in women of reproductive age. While many cysts are asymptomatic and resolve

spontaneously, some may present with abdominal pain, bloating, menstrual irregularities, or infertility. Conventional management typically involves hormonal regulation or surgical excision, which may be associated with recurrence.

In Ayurveda, such conditions can be correlated with Yonivyapad or Granthi where vitiated Kapha and Vata doshas obstruct normal Artavavaha srotas function. Management emphasizes balancing doshas, enhancing Agni (digestive fire), clearing srotas, and restoring normal menstrual physiology.

Samprapti Ghatakas are

Dosha – Vatadosha and Kaphadosha.

Dushya – Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, Arthava.

Srotas – Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Mamsavaha, Medhovaha and Arthavavaha Srotas.

Rogamarga – Abhyantara

Vyaktasthana – Garbhashaya

Udbhavasthana – Amapakwashaya

Agni – Jataragni and Dhatwagni.

This paper presents a case report demonstrating successful management of an ovarian cyst with Ayurvedic interventions.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 24-year-old female presented with complaints of lower abdominal heaviness, pelvic pain during menses. Ultrasonography revealed a left ovarian cyst measuring 4× 3.7 cm. The patient wanted Ayurvedic management to avoid surgical intervention as she had already undergone laproscopic ovarian chocolate cystectomy.

Methods (Intervention)

The treatment was planned with a focus on Kapha-Vata shamana, Agnivardhana, and Srotoshodhana.

1. Shamana therapy

- Kanchanara guggulu (2BD) – known for reducing Granthi and Arbuda.^[4]

- Daruharidra ghanvati(2 BD) – .Ovarian cysts resemble Kaphaja-Granthi / Arbuda in yoni. Daruharidra Ghanvati works as Kapha-Pitta shaman → reduces cystic growth & Shothahara → reduces ovarian swelling

2. Shodhan therapy

- Deepan – Pachan for 3 days followed by yogabasti

- Deepan – Pachan – Tb.Aroyawardini 2 BD

Hingawashtak churn 3gm BD with goghrit + pratham kawal

- **Yogabasti**

Anuwasana – Sahachar tail

Niruha- Dashamooltriphalakwath

“*Bastih vātasya shreshṭhaḥ*” — (*Charaka Siddhi Sthana 1/39*)

Effect

Apana Vata sthana shuddhi → restores normal ovulatory function.

Srotoshodhana → clears obstruction in Artavavaha srotas.

Improves pelvic circulation and hormonal coordination.

Thus, Yogabasti (alternating Niruha and Anuvasana) works both as cleansing (shodhana) and nourishing (snehana).

3. Pathya-apathya

- Diet: Light, easily digestible food, avoidance of guru (heavy), snigdha (oily), and junk foods.

- Lifestyle: Adequate rest, avoidance of stress, and daily mild exercise.

3. Duration: 3 months of therapy with periodic follow-up.

RESULTS

- Clinical improvement: The patient reported reduction in abdominal heaviness, pelvic pain during menses.
- Objective findings: Follow-up ultrasonography at 3 months showed regression of the ovarian cyst.
- Safety: No adverse effects were reported during the treatment.

DISCUSSION

Ovarian cysts can be correlated with Granthi in Ayurveda, caused by Vata-Kapha dosha vitiation. The formulations used acted synergistically:

- Kanchanara guggulu possesses Lekhana (scraping) and Granthi hara properties, traditionally indicated for cystic swellings.^[4]

- Daruharidra ghanvati(2 BD) – .Ovarian cysts resemble Kaphaja-Granthi / Arbuda in yoni.Daruharidra Ghanvati works as Kapha-Pitta shaman → reduces cystic growth & Shothahara → reduces ovarian swelling.

- Sahachar tail anuwasana

“Sahacharo vatakaphaharo balyah srotoshodhakah” — (Bhavaprakasha Nighantu, Guduchyadi Varga 156)

➤ Action in Ovarian Cyst

Vatahara & Snigdha guna pacify Apana vata.

Srotoshodhaka action clears Artavavaha srotas → improves follicular flow.

Yonishoolahara action relieves pelvic pain & congestion.

Improves Rakta & Artava pravartana (restores normal menstruation and ovulation).

-Dashamotriphalakwath Niruha

• “Dashamoolam vata-kaphaharani shothaghni cha” — (Charaka Samhita Sutra Sthana 4/12)

• Triphala tridoshaghni rasayana lekhami shothahara cha” — (Charaka Samhita Sutra Sthana 4/11)

Dashamoola + Triphala provide Lekhana, Shothahara, Srotoshodhana actions.

Reduces inflammation and clears obstruction around ovaries and fallopian tubes.

Enhances hormonal balance and ovarian function.

Modern research supports these actions. Studies have shown that Bauhinia variegata (Kanchanara) has anti-tumor and anti-proliferative activity, while Crataeva nurvala (Varuna) is effective in urinary and cystic disorders.^[7,8]

BEFORE

This case suggests that Ayurvedic interventions can offer a non-invasive and holistic alternative in ovarian cyst management, though larger controlled trials are required for validation.

CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic management with Kanchanara guggulu, Varunadi kwatha, and Ashokarishta, along with diet and lifestyle modification, showed promising results in resolving an ovarian cyst. This case underscores the role of Ayurveda as a safe and effective alternative to surgical or hormonal therapy.

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